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AMENDING ARTICLE 6 OF THE NORTH ATLANTIC TREATY TO EXPLICITLY ENSURE ARTICLE 5 COVERS THE SPACE OBJECTS OF PARTIES

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ABSTRACT

Outer space and the space objects of Parties to the *North Atlantic Treaty* have emerged as indispensable components in the North Atlantic Treaty Organization's (NATO) mission to ensure collective self-defence and deter aggression. However, the text of the North Atlantic Treaty has no mention of outer space nor the Parties' space objects. Article 5 of the North Atlantic Treaty confirms the doctrine of collective self-defence. Instead, it is Article 6 which outlines what territories and what assets of the Parties are covered by Article 5. Parties' space objects are not assets currently listed within Article 6.

This omission leaves the space objects of Parties outside the bounds of Article 5 and therefore vulnerable to interference or armed attack. NATO's current approach to outer space and Parties' space objects is entirely too weak in certifying Article 5's application to this domain and such objects. Such weakness is confirmed when looking at NATO's current approach to cyberspace and Article 5, which is nearly identical to its approach to outer space. Recent disregard for NATO's non-binding statements on Article 5's application to cyberspace implies it will have equal disregard for Article 5's application to space objects.

To prevent such undermining of NATO's commitment to collective self-defence and deterrence, an amendment should be made to prong two of Article 6 of the North Atlantic Treaty. The language "or space objects of any of the Parties when launching to or operating in outer space" should be added to the end of prong two. Such an amendment would ensure that NATO's doctrine of collective self-defence remains rock-solid and continues to deter threatening states. The strength of NATO lies in the certainty of its response to aggression and, most importantly, armed attacks.

KEYWORDS: North Atlantic Treaty, Article 5, Article 6, Outer Space.

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1. THE NORTH ATLANTIC TREATY'S CURRENT COLLECTIVE DEFENCE DOCTRINE

1.1. *The Current State of Articles 5 and 6 of the North Atlantic Treaty*

Article 5 of the North Atlantic Treaty serves as the bedrock of NATO's collective defence alliance. Article 5 makes clear that:

The Parties agree that an armed attack against one or more of them in Europe or North America shall be considered an attack against them all and consequently they agree that, if such an armed attack occurs, each of them, in exercise of the right of individual or collective self-defence recognised by Article 51 of the Charter of the United Nations, will assist the Party or Parties so attacked by taking forthwith, individually and in concert with the other Parties, such action as it deems necessary, including the use of armed force, to restore and maintain the security of the North Atlantic area.²

The provisions of Article 5 have ensured the collective security of all NATO members since its foundation in 1949. The certainty of collective self-defence created by Article 5 maintained the security of NATO Parties through the Cold War and, to this day, continues to protect Parties in the face of war in Europe involving Russia. For 76 years, Article 5 has been successful in deterring aggression and armed attack against Parties, making NATO the most successful military alliance in human history.

Although Article 5 confirms collective self-defence in response to an armed attack against a Party, it is Article 6 of the North Atlantic Treaty which determines what will be considered an armed attack for the purpose of invoking Article 5 by a Party. Article 6 outlines that:

For the purpose of Article 5, an armed attack on one or more of the Parties is deemed to include an armed attack:

on the territory of any of the Parties in Europe or North America, on the Algerian Departments of France, on the territory of [Türkiye] or on the Islands under the jurisdiction of any of the Parties in the North Atlantic area north of the Tropic of Cancer;

on the forces, vessels, or aircraft of any of the Parties, when in or over these territories or any other area in Europe in which occupation forces of any of the Parties were stationed on the date when the Treaty entered into force or the Mediterranean Sea or the North Atlantic area north of the Tropic of Cancer.³

Article 6 places clear territorial and asset limitations on when an armed attack is covered by Article 5. Specifically, Article 6 makes no mention of Article 5 covering outer space or the space objects of Parties operating in such a domain. The furthest reach of Article 5 allowed by Article 6 is in prong two related to aircraft over the territories of Parties articulated in prong one, falling well short of extending to outer space and the space objects of Parties.

1.2. *The Shortcomings of Article 6 of the North Atlantic Treaty*

A plain reading of Article 6 reasonably leads to the conclusion that Article 5 does not apply to outer space nor the space objects of Parties operating in this domain. Such a reality leaves the space objects of Parties dangerously exposed to interference and armed attack by malicious actors and states. Lacking coverage

² North Atlantic Treaty, Apr. 4, 1949, 63 Stat. 2241, 34 U.N.T.S. 243, art. 5.

³ North Atlantic Treaty, Apr. 4, 1949, 63 Stat. 2241, 34 U.N.T.S. 243, art. 6.

by Article 5, Parties' space objects invite meddling by hostile actors and states due to the lack of an ensured collective defence response to armed attacks against such assets.

Leaving Parties' space objects outside the purview of Article 5 is highly irresponsible, given that NATO Parties rely so heavily on space-based assets to ensure their defence and security. Whether on land or sea, in air or cyberspace, NATO missions and operations utilize and rely on space-based assets to always ensure collective self-defence in all desired circumstances. Leaving the space objects of Parties and space as a domain beyond the bounds of Article 5 makes such vital objects vulnerable to interference and armed attack. This reality calls into question NATO's willingness to protect Parties' space objects from armed attack and erodes the certainty of collective self-defence, the bedrock of NATO since its inception.⁴

The aforementioned extension of Article 5 to "aircraft operating over only certain portions of Parties' territories" would be difficult, if not impossible, to extend to space objects. For starters, the reference to aircraft operating *over* specific territories of Parties can reasonably be inferred to mean a Party's sovereign airspace. Thus, extending this language to outer space and its prohibition on sovereignty would directly violate international space law.

Article 1 of the Convention on International Civil Aviation (Chicago Convention) makes clear that "The contracting States recognize that every State has complete and exclusive sovereignty over the airspace above its territory."⁵ However, Article II of the 1967 Outer Space Treaty (OST) also makes clear that "[o]uter space, including the Moon and other celestial bodies, is not subject to national appropriation by claim of sovereignty, by means of use or occupation, or by any other means."⁶ All NATO Parties are States Parties to the Chicago Convention, while only four NATO Parties, Albania, Latvia, Montenegro, and North Macedonia, are not also States Parties to the OST, with none of the four being considered space-faring nations.

The sovereignty over airspace outlined in the Chicago Convention is irreconcilable with the non-appropriation principle of the Outer Space Treaty. Therefore, trying to extend the existing language of Article 6 related to Article 5 covering Parties' airplanes over certain territories to also include Parties' space objects would violate Article II of the Outer Space Treaty, considering Article 1 of the Chicago Convention. Furthermore, even if these two treaties could be reconciled, because space objects constantly orbit around the Earth, the space objects of the Parties would only be temporarily located over the specific territories listed in prong one of Article 6. Moreover, trying to argue that space objects are essentially aircrafts to extend Article 5 to such objects would be fanciful, given the undeniable distinction between aircraft and space objects as categorized military assets.

1.3. *The Shortcomings of NATO's Current Approach to Space*

Absent explicit treaty language in the North Atlantic Treaty related to Article 5 applying to outer space and space objects, NATO has attempted to remedy this dangerous omission in an entirely unsatisfactory manner. At the June 2021 Brussels NATO Summit, NATO leaders limited themselves to saying that attacks to, from, or within space *could* lead to the invocation of Article 5 on a *case-by-case basis*.⁷ No mention of Parties' space objects being covered by Article 5. The glaring issue with this approach to space by NATO leaders is that it is not in any way internationally legally binding on Parties. At best, it is

⁴ Unal, B. (2019). *Cybersecurity of NATO's Space-based Strategic Assets*. Chatham House. The Royal Institute of International Affairs.

⁵ International Civil Aviation Organization. (1980). *Convention on international civil aviation*, (6th ed., Doc 7300/6), art. 1.

⁶ Treaty on Principles Governing the Activities of States in the Exploration and Use of Outer Space, including the Moon and Other Celestial Bodies, Jan. 27, 1967, 18 U.S.T. 2410, 610 U.N.T.S. 205.

⁷ North Atlantic Treaty Organization. "NATO's Approach to Space." *North Atlantic Treaty Organization*, 30 July 2025, www.nato.int/en/what-we-do/deterrence-and-defence/natos-approach-to-space.

a recognition that outer space is a potential new domain in which Article 5 must extend to, but at worst, it is nothing but empty words.

Regardless, such statements by NATO leaders create no binding legal obligations on Parties to treat armed attacks in outer space or against space objects as being covered by Article 5, as they must with territories and military assets listed in Article 6. More concerning, however, is the use by NATO leaders of flimsy language like “could” or “case-by-case” to describe the possible application of Article 5 to outer space. This language is surely lacking when compared to the concrete and unambiguous language found throughout the North Atlantic Treaty. Such ambiguous language by NATO leaders can in no way be expected to communicate to malicious actors and states that NATO is serious about ensuring collective self-defence in outer space and safeguarding the Parties’ space objects. To illustrate this failure, one needs only look at the efficacy of NATO leaders and their language concerning how Article 5 applies to cyberspace.

1.4. *A Comparison of NATO’s Current Approaches to Cyberspace and Space*

At the very same June 2021 NATO summit in Brussels, NATO leaders repeated nearly identical language used to describe Article 5 and outer space when talking about Article 5’s applicability to cyberspace. NATO leaders stated that malicious cyber activities *might* be considered an armed attack which *could* be considered an armed attack, determined on a *case-by-case basis*.⁸ Just like outer space, NATO leaders’ weak and non-binding language regarding Article 5 and cyberspace places cyberspace in an ambiguous and vulnerable position, inviting intervention and armed attack by malicious actors and states. Unlike outer space and Parties’ space object which lack meaningful examples of being threatened with armed attack by malicious actors and states, there are ample cases of cyberspace and Parties’ cyber capabilities being interfered with and targeted for hypothetical armed attacks.

Since Russia’s full-scale invasion of Ukraine in 2022, hostile cyberspace operations by Russia against NATO Parties have increased dramatically in both frequency and scale.⁹ In the face of NATO leaders’ ambiguous language concerning Article 5, cyberspace, and space objects, the continued and growing malicious cyber activities against NATO should be perceived as demonstrating that the statements made at the 2021 Brussels summit go unheeded. By leaving cyberspace in a grey zone related to Article 5, NATO leaders have failed to deter threatening states from acting against NATO Parties in cyberspace. Continued interference with the Parties’ cyber infrastructure and capabilities casts doubts on Article 5 supposedly being applicable to both cyberspace and space objects, undermining NATO’s commitment to collective self-defence.

It should be noted that some NATO leaders have defended ambiguous language relating to Article 5’s coverage. Former NATO Secretary-General Jens Stoltenberg argued that intentional vagueness in defining Article 5’s coverage related to cyberspace specifically acts as a deterrent and forces threatening states to second guess that viability of malicious cyber activities against NATO Parties.¹⁰ However, the aforementioned increase in malicious cyber activities against NATO Parties casts doubt on such a presumption. Instead, this potentially signals that ambiguous language invites threatening states to test the coverage of Article 5 when vague in order to chip away at the certainty it is designed to provide.

NATO leaders used nearly identical language to describe Article 5 and space objects. The ongoing malicious cyber activities directed against NATO Parties demonstrate that ambiguous language fails to deter threatening states. NATO should expect the same failure relating to the Parties’ space objects, given the use of identical language. The failure of the non-binding statements made by NATO leaders in 2021 to

⁸ North Atlantic Treaty Organization. “Cyber Defence.” North Atlantic Treaty Organization, 30 July 2024, www.nato.int/en/what-we-do/deterrence-and-defence/cyber-defence.

⁹ Dynner, A. M. (2023). Russia continuing cyberthreats against NATO countries. *PISM Bulletin*, 172, 2291.

¹⁰ Prucková, M. (2022). Cyber attacks and Article 5—a note on a blurry but consistent position of NATO. *The NATO Cooperative Cyber Defence Centre of Excellence (CCDOE)*.

deter malicious cyber activity makes clear that an unambiguous and explicit binding application of Article 5 to Parties' space objects is necessary to deter threatening states.

1.5. *The Present and Future Threat to NATO Space Objects*

Although the space objects of a NATO Party have yet to be physically targeted by a threatening state, it is important to recognize that such a targeting remains possible in the future. Specifically, Russia has successfully tested anti-satellite weapons.¹¹ The existence of such weapons makes the possible targeting of NATO Parties' space objects no longer a question of possibility, but probability. The weak language currently employed by NATO to describe Article 5's coverage of space objects may increase that probability in light of identical language failing to deter continued malicious cyber activities. In a world where modern militaries are increasingly reliant on space objects for operations, is it wise to leave such vital objects outside the explicit coverage of Article 5?

2. A BETTER COLLECTIVE DEFENCE DOCTRINE INCORPORATING OUTER SPACE

2.1. *Proposed Changes to Article 6 of the North Atlantic Treaty*

To ensure that it is clear that outer space and Parties' space objects are covered by Article 5 to deter both malicious actors and states alike, binding change to the North Atlantic Treaty's language is necessary. Specifically, the second prong of Article 6 of the North Atlantic Treaty should be amended to include Parties' space objects as assets covered by Article 5. An amendment to the second prong of Article 6 should read as follows:

on the forces, vessels, or aircraft of any of the Parties, when in or over these territories or any other area in Europe in which occupation forces of any of the Parties were stationed on the date when the Treaty entered into force or the Mediterranean Sea or the North Atlantic area north of the Tropic of Cancer, *or space objects of any of the Parties when launching to or operating in outer space.*

The inclusion of "or space objects of any of the Parties when launching to or operating in outer space" at the end of the second prong of Article 6 would make unequivocally clear that the Parties' space objects are covered by Article 5. Such an amendment would make threatening actors and states think twice about interfering with or attacking Parties' space object, for fear of Article 5 retaliation.¹²

Furthermore, the specific language of this amendment would not otherwise unintentionally expand Article 5's application beyond the domains and assets articulated by either prong of Article 6. Article 6 has clear limitations on the territorial extension of Article 5, wishing to keep its application contained to the North Atlantic region. French Guiana is an ideal example, which, due to its geographical location south of the Tropic of Cancer, is not a territory covered by Article 6. However, French Guiana remains the primary and preferred launch location for many European Parties' space objects. The language of the proposed amendment would ensure that when any future space object is transported to or assembled in French Guiana, it would not be covered by Article 6, but once said objects were launched into or operating in space, Article 6, and therefore Article 5, would apply.

By limiting the protection of Parties' space objects to only when they are launching into or operating in outer space, the amendment would avoid inadvertently expanding such protection of Article 5 to geographic regions and territories not originally desired to be covered at the inception of Article 6. Moreover, by limiting Article 5's coverage to only Parties' space objects and not outer space itself, the proposed amendment would comply with Article II of the OST and its requirement of non-appropriation.

¹¹ Sankaran, J. (2022). Russia's Anti-Satellite Weapons. *Arms Control Today*, 52(2), 14-19.

¹² Person, R., & McFaul, M. (2022). What Putin fears most. *Journal of Democracy*, 33(2), 18-27.

2.2. *The Legal Procedure for Amending the North Atlantic Treaty*

The process for amending the second prong of Article 6 of the North Atlantic Treaty is governed by Article 12. Article 12 permits that “[a]fter the Treaty has been in force for ten years, or at any time thereafter, the Parties shall, if any of them so requests, consult together for the purpose of reviewing the Treaty,”¹³ The hurdle of requiring that a Party request consultation and review of the treaty for purposes of amending would prove difficult to overcome. As of the writing of this paper, no Party has signalled its interest in amending the North Atlantic Treaty to address space objects. Therefore, before the proposed amendment to the second prong of Article 6 can even be considered, a NATO Party will have to request consultation and review. This paper, in part, hopes to bring the issue of Article 5’s lacking coverage of space objects to the attention of NATO Parties in the hope that consultation and review will be requested.

For the sake of continuing this analysis, hypothetically, if such a request were made and the proposed amendment was accepted as necessary, the actual amendment of the treaty itself would require unanimous ratification by all Parties in line with their respective constitutional processes, in line with Article 11.¹⁴ This would undoubtedly be a long and arduous process, potentially taking years. Such a reality highlights the need to raise this issue now and begin lobbying the whole of the NATO alliance to take seriously the issue of amending Article 5 to explicitly cover space objects and to start taking concrete steps towards making such an amendment a reality in line with Articles 11 and 12.

3. CONCLUSION

Outer space and the space objects of Parties have become integrated and vital components of NATO’s continued success in ensuring collective defence and deterring armed aggression. However, the ambiguities surrounding Article 5’s applicability to outer space and Parties’ space objects risk leaving a dangerous gap in NATO’s defensive guarantees. The current state of NATO’s approach to outer space and Parties’ space objects is entirely inadequate given their importance to NATO’s mission. NATO must learn from recent disregard for its non-binding statements related to cyberspace and Article 5 and ensure such disregard is not extended Parties’ space objects. The surest way to make it explicit that Article 5 does apply to Parties’ space objects is by amending prong two of Article 6. This would leave no room for doubt that Parties’ space objects are protected by Article 5 and would instil confidence that NATO is committed to the doctrine of collective self-defence in all domains and for all assets.

¹³ North Atlantic Treaty, Apr. 4, 1949, 63 Stat. 2241, 34 U.N.T.S. 243, art. 12.

¹⁴ North Atlantic Treaty, Apr. 4, 1949, 63 Stat. 2241, 34 U.N.T.S. 243, art. 11.